

Lecturers' Multimedia Technology Skills for Global Competitiveness in Public Universities in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study investigated lecturers' multimedia technology skills for global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers State. The purpose of the study was to examine the ways technological skills can be enhance global competitiveness. Four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. The population comprised 128 academic staff in the Department of Educational Management from the three (3) public universities, namely: Ignatius Ajuru University of Education with 44 academic staff, Rivers State University, 51, and University of Port Harcourt, 33, respectively. A sample size of 128 lecturers was drawn using census sampling technique. A validated instrument titled "Lecturer Multimedia Technology Skill for Global Competitiveness in Public University questionnaire" (LMTSGCPUQ) was used for data collection. The reliability coefficient gave 0.88 for the study, a modified four-point Likert's scale was used. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The criterion means of 2.50, was interpreted as accepted and below 2.50 was interpreted as rejected. The result revealed that lecturers agreed that video technology, cyber security, troubleshoot skills, among others as the innovative and 21st century academic skills required for global competitiveness in public universities. It was concluded that creating multimedia technology skills would develop lecturers' mental skills and culture for a competitive advantage. It was recommended that stakeholders in education should encourage the use of multimedia technology skills for quality education delivery, and education managers should engage the services of experience facilitators in order to properly guide lecturers on technology skills related areas, and that non-governmental agencies should support to provide a stable network supply to boost the use of technological devices for teaching and learning in public university.

Keywords: Lecturers, Multimedia, technology skills, global competitiveness, public universities, Rivers State.

Introduction

The journey to acquire 21st century technological academic skills and knowledge economy, begins with embracing the culture of digital technology for long useful life. Surely innovators lead the way in this fast changing knowledge driven age. Today's use of multimedia classroom system along with e-learning, opens up a world of learning, and has contributed tremendous in the modern day school management. Education is a watch word that builds on the premise of discovery of new ideas, and help in creating something of value. Using effective pedagogical skills helps to make permanent impact on both teacher and students by helping them to become better professionals in their field of endeavours. However, the school cannot achieve this laudable objective if the lecturers are not well equipped with concrete tools skill to help them think creatively in performance of their duties.

The term lecturer, is an academic expert whose job is to conduct research and inculcate skills and knowledge to the learner to fit in adequately for a competitive advantage. Historically and even now, academic work involves research, teaching and community service. Today multimedia technology skill driven teaching, requires the culture of high productive thinking individuals and as well plays a significant role in school and university development, and lecturer are the indispensable tools to achieve this laudable objective. This is because students attend lectures with intension to acquire relevant skill, concepts and theories related to their course work in order to become professionals in their field of endeavour. The use of multimedia technology skills for effective teaching is trending and have positive and progressive impact that develop system of thought, as it focus as on critical thinking, creativity, thereby providing experience such as problem solving related activity. Its utilization, it is believed, will enhance job productivity of lecturers' in Nigeria. The lecturers are the facilitators of the learning, and as the 21st century lecturers they develop in the learner higher order thinking skill, knowledge of technology and effective strategies and communication for global competitiveness.

It is quite glaring and today that there is a paradigm shift in knowledge to knowledge economy, and what makes university system different from others is their search for quality higher education that would prepare them to fit in into 21st century knowledge driven economy which foster critical and innovating thinking individuals for the world of work. Multimedia classroom involves the use of laptops, projectors, projector wall screen, audio video, internet connection, portable devices and so on to facilitate instruction and promote career development and advancement. It is at the same time used to empower lecturers and learners with wider scope in technology awareness and acquisition of skill crucial to succeed in today's global knowledge economy. However, mastery of technology skill in multimedia classroom are the fundamental basis to achieve result. This is because technology skill promotes and facilitate efficient multimedia classroom teaching and learning process to

achieve a predetermine goal. These technology skills include: video conferencing, cyber security, troubleshoot, coding, technical support, artificial intelligent and word processing skill and so on. Today the increase awareness of internet technology in knowledge driven economy as a viable means to increase efficiency, has necessitated the need for lecturers to embrace and be technological compliant in this information age and knowledge economy world this is an ingredient to develop intellectual skill in pursuit of their career in line with global best practices. The use of multimedia instructional design provides a comprehensive framework to develop competent digital skill for both lecturer and aid the learner to learn faster and better in modern day school system. However, one of the unique features of multimedia instructional design skill is that it aroused learner's interest to learn faster because multimedia is often associated with a pictorial excerpt that makes teaching and learning more interesting.

It is believed that establishing any technological tool in classroom is like breeding harvest field of learning that form habitual; life style in technology related areas for a long useful life. As technology advances machine has become able to perform certain task that traditionally had not been done by human being. Moreover, survival of any organization depends on how competent and compliant work force are since it is in their best ability to project them to the world of work in line with global best practices. In this respect lecturers have to acquire relevant ICT skills to enable them to advance to the course of the school

In the same vein, Patel (2011) conducted a study on the essence of multimedia technology on communication skills and found that for effective preparation of digital educational content, both hardware and software technologies, working knowledge of ICT is needed and many lecturers lack this knowledge.

In a related perspective, university education in Nigeria is a transformation stage that requires high productive thinking, creativity and innovative manpower (lecturers) that are technologically compliant to transform and improve the organizational performance. Many higher institutions of learning today are yet to embrace the use of multimedia technology learning facilities to improve learning effectiveness. It is therefore important to promote the culture of digital technology in the school system. Using multimedia technology instructional design in the 21st century classroom shapes the direction of the school and provides a conducive environment to other acquire skill with ease.

Early learning is like engraving on stone, competence, creativity which create an atmosphere and path way for global competitiveness capacity to use technology to create future for a significant turnaround. To innovate is to bring in novel touch, and explore ideas that would stand the test of time and also help to improve organizational performance.

Equipping lecturers with multimedia technology and new teaching aids method, requires the development the culture of using digital technologies. A multimedia instructor creates a leaning environment in the classroom that provides the learner with the opportunity to acquire 21st century academic skills. The introduction of multimedia technology in classroom learning, have made the lecturer to develop and discover new teaching aids even in subject

that are usually taught using traditional methods as to draw the attention of learners from different background. Buttressing this claim, Ikegusi and Modebelu (2016) observed that knowledge on how to use the computer and its peripheries has become an essential tool in the education tasks. These suggest that modern lecturers are expected to be technologically compliant in impartation of knowledge and skills to the learner, particularly in decisive skills such as, analytical thinking, problem –solving and creative thinking skills. It is in this wise that Achuonye & Ajoku (2008) declared that education is built on the premise of modern ideas, modern strategy, of doing things, compatible with changing educational goals. This implies that educational innovation is imperative especially in the tertiary institution of learning where high productive thinking is essential for effective performance of educational tasks.

Consequently, education is determined by its value, it implies that Continuous technological advancement has become essential in classroom teaching and learning. Changes in curriculum content is one of the surest means to build and develop individuals to be professional in various facet of life. Succinctly, the emphasis these days is centred on the use of technology to achieve effective academic results. To nurture lecturers with this 21st century skills for global competitiveness in public universities, has therefore become very imperative, and this requires attention. This is the subject matter of this present study. However, this study will be reviewed under the following headings: lecturers' multimedia technology skills, video conferencing skill, cyber security skill, and troubleshooting skills.

Statement of the problem

The rising awareness of acquiring multimedia classroom skills as to create a sustainable future, and improve service delivery in public universities, has been recognized globally. This has necessitated the need for university lecturers to be technologically inclined, in order to foster critical thinking for long useful life. Preliminary observation suggests that many university lecturers are not technologically complaint and may not be effective in performance of their duties for the development of 21st century academic skills and knowledge. Penuel et al (2010) admits that the prime obstacle in implementing effective multimedia classroom are the lecturers as many of them do not have technical support to operate and manipulate the computer. Consequences of this limitation include low productivity among university lecturers and attendance low academic achievement among universities students.

Based on the above expressed backdrop, there is need for university lecturers, to be technologically complaint, because it provides a wide range of relevant knowledge skill, an attitude necessary for individuals to be a better professional in their field of endeavour, and a sine-qua-non for healthy global competitiveness.

Aim and objective of the study

The aim of this study is to examine lecturers' multimedia Technology skills for global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers State. Specifically, the study tends to achieve the following objectives:

1. To investigate the various lecturers' multimedia technology skills for global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.
2. To identify the extent lecturers' use of use of multimedia technology skill relating on cyber security skill to enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.
3. To examine the extent lecturers' use of multimedia technology skills relating to video technology skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.
4. To determine the extent lecturers' use of multimedia technology skills relating to trouble shoot skills enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.

Research questions

1. What are the various lecturers' multimedia technology skills for global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state?
2. To what extent does lecturers use of cyber security skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state?
3. To what extent does lecturers' use of video technology skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state?
4. To what extent lecturers' use of trouble shoot skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state?

Hypotheses

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on how various lecturers' multimedia technology skills for global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers' use of cyber security skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.

HO₃: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers' use of video technology skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.

HO₄: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers' use of troubleshoot skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.

Lecturers' multimedia technology skills

In recent time, the pervasiveness of technology in teaching and learning outcomes is perhaps most paramount for healthy school functioning. We are in a proliferation "wired" world kudos to advances in communication technology and the internet. Technology in today's world has found its root in every corner of the world to enhance competitive advantage. The fundamental premise of multimedia classroom is simply, incorporating a technology into the

classroom for effective teaching strategy for optimum productivity. The use of multimedia in the classroom is facilitated by communication technology and internet, which blends operations and deals with wide range of technology application in the classroom teaching and learning.

Technology skills are those skills that increase and promote lecturer effectiveness in multimedia classroom instructional delivery. These skills include video technology skills, cyber security, troubleshoot, technical skill, artificial intelligence skill among others. These digital skills widen lecturer's mental capability in managing effective multimedia classroom for global competitiveness. Today the use of digital skills or technology skills has made instructional delivery more interesting and enjoyable. Teaching and learning can be done seamlessly through the use of skype, zoom, artificial intelligence among others. Conceptualizing multimedia classroom skills, Penuel et al (2010) contended that the use of multimedia classroom facilitates teaching, provide much scope to the students to 'optimize, synthesize and develop eye catching experience of visible content to enhancing their learning.

Multimedia classroom is indispensable component of modern day learning environment. These technologies are found in many institutions of learning in an innovative manner and motivate the student to learn faster. In a traditional classroom setting, focus is the teacher provides the entire knowledge and instruction, using multimedia instructional technique skill allow students to explore things for themselves, support students to be quick learners, problem solvers and more suitable to seek information in their learning process.

This calls for lecturers to be innovative in performance of their statutory roles. This is because the use of multimedia skill promotes culture of self-productiveness and provision of innovative solution and effective strategies to improve student performance. The world today is looking for high productive thinking minded and capable of adding value to education. Virtually today, there is no administrative work in school management that can be done without the use of computer technology to achieve result.

Escoe (2009) contended that technology in classroom contributes integration of various teaching and learning strategies, ie 'active learning, cooperative learning, 'and other learning techniques' into a seamless whole'. The objective is to enhance multimedia based classroom instructional and to the ability of learners to acquire knowledge with ease. The unique feature of multimedia classroom is that it is more effective for learners who learn via observing instructional process, and as well those who learn through listening.

Objectively, the emphasis this day is on technological base approach to content study. Teaching and learning online such as presentation and online course can be done via multimedia regulated technology, and other social media. This is because of the increasing awareness and acceptance of education as an important vehicle for social economic development.

Okoloha and Ile (2007) stated that the presence of technology has opened a new world of learning which has drastically increased output among technology users. They stressed further that the new technology call for updates of education programs and training to assist

lecturers and students to acquire possess relevant skills and competencies for achievement of goals and objectives. Ayo (2011) stated there is a great development in information technology through the use of computer. He maintained that as the society becomes more computerized, and technologically sophisticated, the need for knowledge and application of computer skills becomes more imperative. It is in this direction that Omofaye (2007) suggested that nations should route to become a successful knowledge economy, by resting on its ability to also imbibe and inculcate the act learning as a society.

Admittedly, many university lecturers today are yet to embrace, and cultivate the culture of digital technology in classroom setting, which enhances the realization of educational objectives. Owing to this Peniel et al (2010) admits that the prime impediment to implementing a successful and effective multimedia classroom learning environment is the teacher. They lack skills to use computer in class and gain technological support to operate devices is most worrisome.

However, Aktumen and Kacar (2013) contended that using computer and internet connection in classroom fosters learner's academic proficiency. In the same vein, Awake (2009) reported that the perverseness of the technology in today's world is perhaps most apparent and knowledge of computer and related technology may be essential for millions of children. They stresses further that many products of science and technology are practical and can save us much time and energy. One of the objectives of teacher's education as enshrine in the National policy on education (2013) is to provide lecturers with intellectual capability and to make them adaptable. Buttressing this, Achuonye (2008) affirmed that teaching method have changed from traditional methods to innovative approach. She stressed further that these methods are opposite end of the continuum and process different characteristics and see technology as more efficient area of knowledge.

Cyber security skills

Cyber security is a skill required of lecturers to possess or acquire in the operation of multimedia instructional delivery. This is because the alarming rate of cyber theft and internet fraudsters is worrisome. The significance of cyber security concerning technology innovation is that it protects authors' train of thought from theft of being copied without prior permission. This is necessary because it allows university system to maintain a competitive advantage and as well keep their product and services save from other competitors. Cyber security helps to protect the digital data on computer network and device from unauthorized access. The importance of cyber security in lecturer multimedia skill is critical and cardinal because cyber security is essential in the use of multimedia classroom as it safe guide different types of data against loss and theft. In this technology driven ear, our life and research work are increasingly dependent online which store data and personal information on computers and other technology devices. Importance of cyber security in this increasingly internet world is supreme as the volume and sophistication of cyber attacker are on alarming rate.

Apparently, as our dependent on this technology driven age grow, so does our vulnerability on this cybercrime. Cyber security helps develop innovative solution for effective strategy in delivering a lecture in a multimedia classroom. Today organizations such as universities, banks, hospitals among others protect their portal from cyber theft. This is because a single breach can have far reaching consequences in today's globalized world. If a lecturer or a student's personal information is stolen in a cyber attack, it could be used to commute identity theft. Some of the most common cyber attack includes:

1. Phishing attacks: as the name implies it is type of cyber attack that involves tricking users into malicious attachment or link this can lead to the theft of sensitive information.
2. Malware attack: Just as the name suggests it is a type of malicious soft ware that can infect computer and devices. This malware can hijack devices, steal information and as well lunch attack on other systems.
3. Man-in-the middle (mitm): This is a type of attack where attackers intercept communication between two parties, this can be done on a network computer or redirecting traffic to a malicious cyber.
4. Ransom-ware attack: As the name implies it encrypts file on the system and demand a ransom to decrypt them. This can lead to loss of important data.

Video technology skills

There is a great gain and contentment in using video technology in a multimedia technology classroom. Video technology inspire and enhances students' academic performance this is because more often it comes with a pictorial excerpt that aroused students' interest to learn faster and better. Video technology let students collaborate on group work or project easily. It is believed that to make multimedia classroom delivery more interesting interactive, there is need to find opportunity that enables students to work in synergy and foster conversation. Also it is easy for students to lose interest if the entire teaching process depends on lecture alone.

Buttering this claim Egunjobi (2012), pointed out that educational media contains materials that have educational content which facilitates the accomplishment of teaching and learning objectives when utilized in institution of learning by lecturers in any educational level. However, Neo and Neo (2009) stated that multimedia technology facilitates students working at alternative pace and the use of it has effect on lecturers' effectiveness and students' academic prowess. This implies that lecturer relevant knowledge with digital skill is the premise to fit in globally for the world of work. This is because advances in communication technology usher in new system of knowledge in instructional delivery that aids both lecturers as well students to be a better professional in their field of endeavours.

In today's technology driven age new technology such as video conferencing, artificial intelligence, zoom, has given lecturers' a wider scope of presenting materials, working with students and thus stimulating the development of strategies that are consistent with new technology. Video conferencing help put project teaching beyond textbooks and connect

learners with digital age world they live in. the use of video conferencing in multimedia classroom has recorded tremendous result and has flourished with the development of different services on the internet. Video conferencing has helped open and distance learning which provide education and training in a more flexible way than the regular one. The pervasiveness of technology in today's world is an essential component of this e-learning technology.

The possibility of using Skype, zoom, artificial intelligence software in instructional delivery can be credited to video technology which help develop lecturers' with mental skill for global competitiveness in today's world of work.

Troubleshoot skills

Experience they say is the best teacher. The primary basis of troubleshooting is to figure out technical glitches that may arise in the course of using computer network in classroom delivery and as well provide a solution to resolve the issue. Most time experience apply is very useful to solving following a troubleshooting model will foster effectiveness and speed. Troubleshoot skill is the skill that can be refined over time, each time you solve a problem you increase your troubleshoot skill by gaining wider experience. It is important to know that before a lecturer embarks on a trouble shoot problem there is need to follow necessary measure to protect data loss from the computer system. Most times troubleshooting techniques such as closing and reopening the program can solve a problem of troubleshooting, it is necessary to try this process before resorting in an extreme measure. Troubleshooting methodologies varies but the following steps are often used, identify the problem, describe the problem, analyse the result, establish a plan, implement the solution, document findings, actions and outcome.

Ayo (2011) who found that there is a great development in information technology through the use of computer. He maintained that as the society becomes more computerized and technology sophisticated, the need for more skills and computer becomes more imperative.

However, Bandung et al (2015) found that the challenges of using multimedia or classroom as include lack of electronic resources, networking, application software, systems, human resources, hardware system and so on. It is germane to note that availability of these devices put in place will promote and sustain healthy school climate and promote teaching and learning. The need for stake holders of education and non-governmental organization to support where necessary, as to ensure implementation of multimedia classroom teaching in tertiary institution to ensure that lecturers comes to lime light in line with global best practices. Drawing from the above therefore, it can be deduced from the foregoing that a multimedia –enabled classroom is a priority for lecturers in the process of imparting knowledge to the vested quarters.

Gao (2011) investigated the problem of multimedia and found that most of the problems originate not from the tools; but lack of expertise on classroom management of the tools.

Globalization

Education has been globalized today with the use of modern technological tool to achieve tremendous result that promotes education system as a significant mile stone for qualitative education delivery. Globalization is a system of ideas, across international boundaries that improves the quality of education worldwide. Globalization empowers the competent of learner to access adapt, and apply knowledge to think independently and collaborate with others to usher new system of thought. However the level to which this can be achieved is determined with the readiness of lecturer to embrace this culture of digital technology. This signify that people can only benefit from globalization if they are endowed with intellectual skills to discover new solution as an essential ingredient to make instructional delivery more better and fulfilling for all.

Objectively, every organization has a competitor, global competitiveness in the context of this paper is the ability and willingness to nurture and provide innovation driven knowledge to achieve sustained high result in order to be more successful than other competitors. In an increasingly technological driven world manager must rise up to the occasion integrate and implement technology-based development strategies to create environment which produce high skill manpower for 21st century academic skill for the world of work. In building a global competitive system in the school the management and lecturers must develop and nurture the unwavering zeal for creativity and commitment in the organization to compete globally. Competitiveness in any setting today is considered as a key characteristics for accessing the success of such organization. It evaluates how institution of learning like school can achieve and maintain qualitative education programme that can stand the test of time, and usher in new strategies that will take the school as institution of learning to an enviable standard.

However, lecturers are the premise on which this can be accomplished, lecturers' knowledge of the subject matter can shape the direction of the school and the society at large. This is because at the head of implementation of curriculum lies the beginning of lecturers; work depends on the teacher. History had it that no nation can make any meaningful stride in its development when less emphasis is placed on teacher's education. This fact came to the fore when the federal government of Nigeria in its National Policy on Education affirmed that teacher education shall continue to be given a major emphasis in its development programme. This suggests that teacher required a broad base knowledge that corresponds to the test of time for a competitive advantage.

The university system was established on the fiber of teaching, research work, and so on to develop intellectual skills, and reimagine the future and discover new solution for an advantageous manner. Quite remarkably the advent of internet technology, which has numerous formats can be communicated over the web has unified technological device into classroom presentation which increases lecturers' abilities to present material that arouse and encourage learners interaction with subject matter. For instance, video animation helps lecturer to bring teaching into life experience.

Methodology

The design for the study was descriptive survey design, the study population comprised 128 teaching staff in the Department of Educational Management from the three (3) selected public universities namely Ignatius Ajuru University of Education with 44 academic staff, Rivers State University 51, and University of Port Harcourt 33 respectively (Source: Office of the HOD in the three selected public university in River state). A sample size of 128 was drawn using census A validated instrument title “Lecturers Multimedia Technology Skills for Global competitiveness for public University in Rivers State” (LMTSGCPU) was used for data collection. The LMTSGCPU was a self-designed instrument with a total of 20 items structured on four-point response options of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1). The LMTSGCPU has two sections of A and B. Section A was used to elicit information about the respondents based on their demographic formations. Section B has two clusters of I and II. Cluster I have ten (10) items that elicited responses on Lecturers Multimedia Technology Skills, while cluster II has ten items on lecturers’ skills respectively. Face validity was done on technology skill by three experts. Two experts are from the Department of Educational Management while the other is from Measurement and Evaluation all from the Faculty of Education, Ignatius AjuruUniversity. The internal consistency reliability coefficient of 0.88 was computed for LMTSGCPU through Cronbach alpha method. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the various lecturers’ multimedia technology skills for global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state?

Table 1: mean and standard deviation on the various lecturers’ multimedia technology skills for global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state

s/n	Various lecturers’ multimedia technology skill for global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state	Male			Female		
		Mean	Std	Decision	Mean	Std	Decision
1	Video technology skill	2.85	.76	Agreed	2.68	.83	Agreed
2	Cyber security skill	3.22	.83	Agreed	3.12	.84	Agreed
3	Troubleshooting skill	2.85	.68	Agreed	2.84	.66	Agreed
4	Artificial intelligence skill	3.35	.89	Agreed	3.19	.97	Agreed
5	Technical support skill	2.57	.86	Agreed	2.58	.86	Agreed
	Aggregate mean and standard deviation	2.97	0.80		2.88	0.83	

Data on table 1 revealed that items with serial numbers 1 to 5 have their various mean values above the criterion mean value of 2.50 and were agreed by the respondents as the various lecturers’ multimedia technology skills for global competitiveness in public universities in

Rivers state. The various lecturers' multimedia technology skills for global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state are video technology skill, cyber security skill, troubleshooting skill, artificial intelligence skill and technical support skill.

Research question 2: To what extent does lecturers' use of cyber security skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state?

Table 2: mean and standard deviation on the extent lecturers use of cyber security skill to enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state

S/N	Extent do lecturers' use of cyber security skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state	Male			Female		
		Mean	Std	Decision	Mean	Std	Decision
6	Coverage for external threats	3.31	.50	High Extent	3.11	.87	High Extent
7	Defence against internal threats	2.85	.98	High Extent	2.86	.94	High Extent
8	Regulatory compliance for security	3.02	.81	High Extent	3.04	.77	High Extent
9	Threat detection, prevention and response	3.19	.78	High Extent	3.05	.89	High Extent
10	Proper security analytics	2.76	.67	High Extent	2.66	.75	High Extent
	Aggregate mean and standard deviation	3.03	0.75	High Extent	2.94	0.84	High Extent

Data on table 2 revealed that items with serial numbers 6 to 10 have their various mean values above the criterion mean value of 2.50 and were agreed that lecturers' use of cyber security skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state to a high extent.

Research Question 3: To what extent does lecturers' use of video technology skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state?

Table 3: mean and standard deviation on the extent lecturers' use of video technology skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state

S/N	Extent do lecturers' use of video technology skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state	Male			Female		
		Mean	Std	Decision	Mean	Std	Decision
11	High –Quality audio-and video	3.43	.50	High Extent	3.20	.66	High Extent
12	Screen share features	3.29	.46	High Extent	3.23	.45	High Extent
13	Multiple device support	3.42	.49	High Extent	3.35	.51	High Extent
14	Schedule a meeting	3.00	.59	High Extent	3.31	.53	High Extent
15	Video recording	3.28	.45	High Extent	2.87	.57	High Extent
		3.28	0.49	High Extent	3.19	0.54	High Extent

Data on table 3 revealed that items with serial numbers 11 to 15 have their various mean values above the criterion mean value of 2.50. The aggregate mean values of 3.28 and 3.19 showed that lecturers' use of video technology skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state to a high extent.

Research question 4: To what extent lecturers' use of trouble shoot skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state?

Table 4: mean and standard deviation on the extent lecturers' use of trouble shoot skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state

S/N	Extent do lecturers' use of troubleshoot skill enhances global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state	Male			Female		
		Mean	Std	Decision	Mean	Std	Decision
16	Identify the problem	3.09	.46	High Extent	3.14	.56	High Extent
17	Establish a theory of possible case	2.67	.85	High Extent	2.62	.50	High Extent
18	Test the theory to determine the cause	2.96	.86	High Extent	2.86	.56	High Extent
19	Establish a plan of action to solve the problem	2.54	.94	High Extent	3.01	.77	High Extent

20	Implement the solution	2.84	.50	High Extent	2.92	.75	High Extent
	Aggregate mean and standard deviation	2.82	0.72	High Extent	2.91	0.63	High Extent

Data on table 4 revealed that items with serial numbers 16 to 20 have their various mean values above the criterion mean value of 2.50. The aggregate mean values of 2.82 and 2.91 showed that lecturers' use of trouble shoot skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state to a high extent.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on various lecturers' multimedia technology skills for global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.

Table 5: t-test of the mean difference between male and female staff on various lecturers' multimedia Technology skills enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state

Gender	N	Mean	Std	Df	t-cal.	Sig.	Alpha level	Decision
Male staff	54	2.97	0.80	126	1.18	.24	.05	Not significant
Female staff	74	2.88	0.83					

Data on table 5 revealed that male staff have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.97 and 0.80 while female staff have mean and standard deviation of 2.88 and 0.83 respectively. With a t-value of 1.18 and degree of freedom of 126, the hypothesis is accepted because the significant value of 0.24 is greater than the alpha 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on various lecturers' multimedia technology skills for global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers' use of cyber security skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.

Table 6: t-test of the mean difference between male and female staff on Lecturers' cyber security skills enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state

Gender	N	Mean	Std	Df	t-cal.	Sig.	Alpha level	Decision
Male staff	54	3.03	0.75	126	2.11	.04	.05	Significant
Female staff	74	3.94	0.84					

Data on table 6 revealed that male staff have mean and standard deviation scores of 3.03 and 0.75 while female staff have mean and standard deviation of 2.94 and 0.84 respectively. With a t-value of 2.11 and degree of freedom of 126, the hypothesis is rejected because the significant value of 0.04 is less than the alpha 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, there is a

significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers' use of cyber security skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers' use of video technology skill to enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.

Table 7: t-test of the mean difference between male and female staff on Lecturers' video technology skills for global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state

Gender	N	Mean	Std	Df	t-cal.	Sig.	Alpha level	Decision
Male staff	54	3.28	0.49	126	3.18	.03	.05	Significant
Female staff	74	3.19	0.54					

Data on table 7 revealed that male staff have mean and standard deviation scores of 3.28 and 0.49 while female staff have mean and standard deviation of 3.19 and 0.54 respectively. With a t-value of 3.18 and degree of freedom of 126, the hypothesis is rejected because the significant value of 0.03 is less than the alpha 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers' use of video technology skill can enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers' use of troubleshoot skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.

Table 8: t-test of the mean difference between male and female staff on Lecturers' troubleshoot skills enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state

Gender	N	Mean	Std	Df	t-cal.	Sig.	Alpha level	Decision
Male staff	54	2.82	0.72	126	3.00	.00	.05	Significant
Female staff	74	2.91	0.63					

Data on table 8 revealed that male staff have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.82 and 0.72 while female staff have mean and standard deviation of 2.91 and 0.63 respectively. With a t-value of 3.00 and degree of freedom of 126, the hypothesis is rejected because the significant value of 0.00 is less than the alpha 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers' use of troubleshoot skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.

Summary of Findings

The findings of the study are summarized as follows:

1. The various lecturers' multimedia technology skills for global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state are video technology skill, cyber security skill, troubleshooting skill, artificial intelligence skill and technical support skill. The hypothesis revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female staff on various lecturers' multimedia technology skills can enhance for global competitiveness in public university in Rivers state
2. It was found that lecturers use of cyber security skill to enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state to a high extent. The hypothesis testing revealed that there is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers' use of cyber security skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.
3. The study revealed that lecturers' use of video technology skill to enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state to a high extent. The hypothesis testing revealed that there is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers' use of video technology skill can enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state.
4. The finding revealed that lecturers' use of trouble shoot skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state to a high extent. The hypothesis testing revealed that there is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers' use of troubleshoot skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state

Discussion of findings

Lecturer's Multimedia technology skill and global competitiveness

The study revealed that the use of multimedia technology skill has become a way to stay innovative, develop lecturers' intellectual skill and as well acquire 21st century academic skill for the world of work. There is no significant difference between the male and female teaching staff on lecturers' multimedia technology skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state. The study was supported by Aktuman & Kacar (2013) who found that using computer and internet classroom foster lecturers and learners academic proficiency.

Cyber security skill and global competitiveness

The study revealed that competent knowledge of cyber security skill widens lecturer's mental capability which scientifically increases lecturers' proficiency in classroom teaching and learning for advantageous manner. There is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female teaching staff on lecturers' cyber security skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state. This study was in agreement with Ayo (2011) who found that there is a great development in information technology through the use of computer. He maintained that as the society becomes more computerized and technology sophisticated, the need for more skills and computer becomes more imperative.

Video technology skill and global competitiveness

The study revealed that use of video technology skill in multimedia classroom learning inspires and enhances students' academic performance which makes them to learn faster and better, widens lecturer's mental capability and proficiency in classroom teaching and learning for competitive advantage. There is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female teaching staff on lecturers' video technology skill enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state. This study was in agreement with Egunjobi (2012), pointed out that educational media contains materials that have educational content which facilitates the accomplishment of teaching and learning objectives when utilized in institution of learning by lecturers in any educational level.

Troubleshoot skill and global competitiveness

The study revealed that the use of troubleshoot skill in multimedia classroom learning is used to locate error message or the cause of a fault in a computer system and as well tackle the relevant software and hardware issues. There is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female teaching staff on lecturers' troubleshoot skill to enhance global competitiveness in public universities in Rivers state. This study was in agreement with Ayo (2011) who found that there is a great development in information technology though the use of computer. He maintained that as the society becomes more computerized and technology sophisticated, the need for more skills and computer becomes more imperative.

Conclusion

It is clear and glaring that the global education is rapidly embracing the new trend of teaching, as an essential ingredient for positive impact. Creating multimedia-based teaching skill would increase and develop teacher's mental skill culture, as well solve learning related issues for a competitive advantage.

Recommendations

The study recommended that:

- i. The stakeholders in education should monitor closely, and encourage the implementation and use of multimedia technology in skill for enhanced quality education delivery.
- ii. Education managers should always engage the services of experienced facilitators in order to properly engage lecturers on technology related skills.
- iii. Non-governmental agencies should support to provide a stable network supply to boost the use of technological devices for enhanced teaching and learning environment.

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